

A potency of good agricultural practices implementation for groundnut in Jambi city

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ABSTRACT

Rapid development of food industry based on groundnut increased the need of this commodity. The world's groundnut export market is dominated by five major producer countries: United States, China (Hong Kong), Singapore, China (Mainland) and South Africa. Indonesia as the world's peanut-producing country is on the 4th rank after China, the United States and Mexico, but has not been able to compete in the export market. It is proven that peanut imports quantity in Indonesia is still high. The enhancement of Indonesian groundnut's productivity can be done through land expansion and the implementation of site-specific technologies in various regions. Jambi City has the potential to develop groundnuts in terms of land, agro-climate and human resources. The constraints are the unavailability of certified good quality seeds, limited application of technology, limited planting area in addition to poor post-harvest handling that resulted impacts on the low quality of products. Groundnuts are generally cultivated as intercropping in rice fields, intercropping between corn, and in yards on limited land so that the average of production becomes low. Groundnut production in Jambi City over the past 10 years has decreased with an average score of 7.48%. Technology input is needed to increase the productivity in order to increase farmers' income. The enhancement of groundnut production and productivity in Jambi city through the implementation of GAP (Good Agricultural Practices), aims to provide quality, safe, sustainable food industry and easy access of raw materials. Food production in urban areas can facilitate distribution and downstream, therefore, it can increase farmers' income.

Keywords: *Groundnut, Good Agricultural Practices, Development Potential, Implementation of Technology*

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has the opportunity as the world groundnut producer country. Groundnut development opportunities in Indonesia is supported by agroclimate conditions which are suitable for the growth of this plant. Groundnuts are able to adapt widely in tropical regions with temperatures of 25

0–30 0C. Temperatures below 18 0C and above 35 0C can hamper the growth of the plant (Awal and Ikeda, 2002). Higher temperature (above 33-34 0C) inhibits pollination and formation of groundnuts (pods) (Prasad et al., 1999; Prasad et al. 2001).

The development of groundnuts to various regions in Indonesia needs to be done in accordance with the availability of land and its agroclimate conditions. Jambi Province continues to develop the potential of groundnuts, including in Jambi City. The area of groundnuts cultivation in Jambi is 4 ha with a productivity of 1.45 tons/ha (BPS 2018). The enhancement of productivity can be achieved with the implementation of GAP (Good Agricultural Practices).

Increased production and productivity of groundnut in Jambi through the implementation of GAP, aims to provide quality, safe, sustainable and easy access of food industry raw materials. Food production in urban areas can facilitate distribution and downstream, resulting in an enhancement of farmers income. This paper discusses the availability of technology and the potential for groundnuts development through the implementation of GAP in Jambi City.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used primary and secondary data. The primary data were direct field observation and interviews with respondents (groundnut farmers in Jambi City). Secondary data were obtained from documents, reports and the authorized agency.

Data collection techniques were as follows:

1. Observations. Direct observation was done on farmer's land in 3 sub-districts, namely East Jambi Subdistrict, Alam Barajo and Pelayangan, as a sample of areas with groundnut planting areas.
2. Interviews. Interviews with farmers were conducted to obtain data in accordance with the research focus.
3. Documentation. Documentation in the form of secondary data including data from BPS, FAO statistics website (FAOstat), data on area and production of the observed sub-districts. In addition, field observations were conducted by collecting the data from surveys using questionnaires and question lists.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Potential Implementation of Good Agricultural Practices in Jambi City

Land Resources

The harvested area of groundnuts in Jambi City decreased during 2012-2015 for about 43.58% despite experiencing an enhancement in 2016 (Table 2).

The decrease in harvested area showed that the limited land area can be used for groundnuts cultivation. Based on the interviews in the field, it was known that the development of groundnuts was not a priority for farmers in Jambi City, because the priority for farmers was the expansion of rice and corn cultivation. The enhancement in land area and production of groundnuts in Jambi that occurred in 2016 showed that there were opportunities for increasing groundnut production in Jambi City, although the average of productivity was still low. Productivity improvement opportunities were found in the implementation of technology to optimize land and climate resources.

Table 2. The Development of Harvested Area and Groundnut Production in Jambi City, 2012-2016.

Year	Harvest Area (ha)	Production (ton)	Productivity (ton ha ⁻¹)
2012	38	95,07	2,50
2013	35	94,69	2,71
2014	20	28,97	1,45
2015	4	5,80	1,45
2016	17	26,36	1,55
Growth 2011-2016	48,56 %	51,17 %	-7,82 %

Source: BPS, processed.

Socio-Economic

The simplest groundnut marketing chain in Jambi City was the farmers-market-district-consumer. Some farmers sold their product to collectors who directly took the products from farmer’s land, then sold the products to the market in the City (Figure 1). Farmers who live far away from the market generally chose the marketing chain of farmers-collector-city market-consumer, because it reduced the transportation costs in product sales. Other marketing opportunities were sales to factories outside the City, as raw material for processed groundnut products.

Figure 1. Groundnut Marketing Scheme of Jambi City

The price of wet groundnuts (with shell) at the farmer's level was Rp. 10.000,- up to Rp. 15.000,- per kg. Peeled and dried groundnuts produced a higher price which was Rp. 16.000,- up to Rp. 17.000,- per kg. Most farmers sold wet groundnuts. Additional incomes of groundnut cultivation obtained by farmers were from the seeds. Some farmers sold dried groundnuts as a seed by Rp. 50.000,- up to Rp. 60.000,- per kg.

The price of groundnuts at the farm level was still determined by the collecting traders, resulting in price fluctuations, especially at the harvest time. A large difference often occurred between the price at the farm level and the market to consumers. Price contracts were needed between producers (farmers) and traders/collectors to maintain the stability of product prices at the farmer level. The development of groundnut processing industries in various regions would greatly support the enhancement in the sale value of the commodity.

Technology Availability

The principles of GAP (Good Agricultural Practices) implementation include soil fertility, crop production technology and sustainable agriculture in relation to ICM (Integrated Crop Management) which was adapted to site-specific agroecology and local wisdom in the community. The general guidelines of ICM of Agricultural Research and Development Agency (Rahmianna et al. 2010), for groundnuts are high-yielding varieties and good quality seeds, land preparation, population management, time management, fertilization, pest control management, irrigation during critical periods, proper harvesting and post-harvest handling. The dominant factor which caused low production of groundnuts according to Paturohman and Sumarno (2014) was drought stress in the generative phase, therefore, setting the planting time was an important factor in groundnut GAP. The implementation of GAP according to location-specific technology was expected to be able to improve groundnut production optimally.

High-Yielding Varieties

High-yielding varieties of groundnuts which have been released by Research Institute for Various Nuts and Tuber Crops, Agricultural Research and Development Agency in 2016 reached 45 varieties that have advantages in terms of production, adaptability, disease resistance and individual market segments (Balitkabi, 2016). Results of some study about several groundnut high-yielding varieties in the dry season in North Sulawesi showed that Kelinci variety produced 1.27 tons ha⁻¹ of fresh pods, compared to other varieties tested, namely Kancil, Domba and Jerapah (Polakitan and Taulu, 2014). Kelinci variety

was a variety that was widely used by farmers in Jambi City, although the seeds used were the seeds from the previous planting. Groundnut farmers in Pelayangan district have been using local seeds since 30 years ago, and the first plant was from Kelinci varieties.

Planting Time and Population

Dominant groundnut areas were acid dry land and tidal land on the edge of Batang Hari River. Planting time on tidal land was done once a year, after the rainy season and floods in July. Planting time on dry land was generally done 1-2 times a year.

Plant population management aimed to optimize the absorption of nutrients by plants. The recommended population of groundnut plants was 250.000-400.000 plants per hectare, with plant spacing of 40 cm x 10 cm, 20 cm x 20 cm, 40 cm x 30 cm x 15 cm (double row) (Sudaryono, 2003). Groundnut plant spacing which was applied by farmers in Jambi City was 20 cm x 30 cm, 40 cm x 20 cm dan 40 cm x 40 cm. Plant spacing of groundnut which was intercropping with corn was 40 cm x 40 cm and corn was 100 cm x 100 cm.

Harvest and Postharvest

In line with increased productivity and improvements in cultivation techniques that refer to the concept of GAP, another important thing that must be considered was post-harvest handling. In general, post-harvest handling of agricultural products including groundnuts was directed to the application of the GHP concept (Good Handling Practice). Groundnuts which included in pod products have the following post-harvest stages; (1) harvesting, (2) threshing the pods, (3) drying, (4) seeding or peeling the pods and (5) storage.

The improvement of post-harvest handling of groundnut was very essential, especially in threshing and drying the pods which were the key activities in maintaining the continuity of raw materials supply that fulfilled the quality standards, both from physical and food safety aspects (Tastra, et.al., 2015). Proper and appropriate post-harvest handling could help to reduce or avoid the groundnuts from Aflatoxin contamination. Aflatoxin was a toxic secondary metabolite compound produced by certain strains of *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* fungi (Horn et al. 2000; Klich 2007). Aflatoxin leads to aflatoxicosis in humans or livestock due to inhaling or consuming high levels of food contaminated by aflatoxin. Aflatoxicosis was a serious problem in developing countries, especially in Asia and Africa. Therefore, it leads to a very serious attention to post-harvest groundnuts handling even though in a relatively small farming scope which became highly important.

Generally, farmers in the location have not been able to implement harvest handling until post-harvest by referring to the concept of GHP, this was due to the lack of facilities and information on post-harvest technology of groundnuts.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. The implementation of groundnut GAP in Jambi City has a prospect that was supported by the availability of natural resources, both land and climate and also human resources, as seen from the optimism of farmers in running groundnut farming..
2. The formation and empowerment of farmer groups were needed to support the development of GAP in Jambi City.
3. The recommendation of GAP technology for spesific location in Jambi City and the downstreaming need to be prepared to support the implementation by farmers.

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